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DIGITAL PHARMACEUTICAL MARKETING: A REVIEW

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ABSTRACT:

'Digital' has become a major part of daily life. All industries have adapted faster to the digital age. However, other than the internet, digital marketing was not entirely acceptable to the pharmaceutical industry. More pharmaceutical companies use social media or e-commerce sites as digital marketing channels in this period. This allows consumers to buy items online. Some organizations strive to grasp the true meaning of emerging technology while others integrate it into a broader marketing plan. However, not all businesses will sell goods online, because they produce prescription medications that cannot be sold online. For example, through social networking sites, Pfizer is involved and attentive to its customers. YouTube, Facebook and Twitter have been used for consumer communication. One of the first companies to start a YouTube channel was Johnson and Johnson. In Quantum Pharmaceuticals and The Specials Lab, North-East pharmaceutical companies deliver e-commerce and digital marketing online ordering for special medicines.

KEYWORDS: Pharmaceutical marketing, digital marketing, digital marketing strategies, e-pharm, social media.

INTRODUCTION:

Some businesses are highly creative in digital development, but the use of digitalisation in pharmaceutical is limited by lack of good case studies [1]. The pharmaceutical industry is not so well suited for web marketing. The sector's cautious conduct, coupled with an unpredictable regulation, has held pharmaceutical industries in check, while financial, technical, manufacturing and business services marketers have been online [2]. In order to adapt increasing uses by patients, mobile social media and online information, medicine professionals (HCP), leading opinion leaders (KOL) and the wider medical fraternity, however, online professional and patient communities have inspired pharmaceutical companies to invest in, and explore, digital marketing strategies within industry guidelines[3].

Types of digital marketing

1. Search engine optimization:

As consumers look for health information, they first turn on the most used search engines, Google, Yahoo or MSN/Bing. Searching for health information is one of

the most frequent online practices for internet users of all ages. SEO is a powerful way of reaching these users. Search ranks are manipulated by using techniques to optimize search engines that offer Google or any other search engine a better search role.

It is therefore an important opportunity for companies using SEO techniques to meet their target audiences. Organizations that cannot be found in search engines miss out on a big chance to meet the target population [4]. Keywords used for titles and URLs, internal links on your own page, back links from other websites, proper image usage of alt tags, and social Networking[5] are critical aspects of search engine optimization.

2. Social Media Marketing^[5]:

Search engines use social media activity as a marketing medium. Facebook posts, twitter retweets and +1s on Google support your search engine search results page position. Social networking marketing allows the business to be directly linked to its customers. It boosts the ideals of the brand and strengthens the company's image. In a public forum, the negative interactions can be reversed by delivering company website notifications and encouraging debate.

3. Pay Per Click Ads^[5]:

If there is insufficient traffic on the company's website, advertisements can be bought on Google. Ads can also be bought directly from other websites via various ad networks. Pay-per-click or PCC adds depend on the keyword used by Google's search engine. Technology for ad analytics allows the organization to assess the success rate of PPC campaigns. The company will pay only if anyone clicks the connection.

4. Email Newsletters^[6]:

Exact Target published its 2012 Channel Preference Survey, suggesting that emails remain the number one direct channel that customers choose for everyday use both for personal and marketing communications. In addition, the widespread use of smart phones and tablets enables customers to easily access emails. The Exact Target report showed that 77% of consumers prefer approved marketing communications via e-mail compared to social and text messaging channels (6%). Email offers customers the feeling of power and personalization in which they can opt for a relationship and only supply the details they want to receive only.

Current scenario and challenges:

The number of Internet users in Asia in 2014 totaled 1405 million, followed by 582.4 million in Europe and rising worldwide every day. This gave the digital age in various sectors a big boost [7].

Digital marketing in every field is a more affordable and time-consuming tool for communicating with consumers than conventional marketing. Digital marketing enables pharmaceutical advertisers to use data to build more strategic relationships with medical professionals and prescribers. However, several businesses still cannot incorporate emerging technology into the broader business strategy [10]. In embracing digital marketing techniques, the pharmaceutical industry faces many obstacles. Inadequate company vision^[11]. Many businesses lack an appropriate vision to

incorporate digital marketing solutions. The tactics are not well described, accepted and internally communicated. In order to validate the vision, define the goals and track the speed of work, good management is essential. The organization does not generally describe the ground force and marketing champions supporting a digital pharmaceuticals view.

1. A lack of digital minds^[10]:

The pharmaceutical industry lacks professional employees who are able to facilitate digital transformation. The employees should be aware of digital marketing as well as the complexities of digital implementation in the pharmaceutical industry to develop digital marketing in the business. Most businesses lack productive employees who grasp the business and the emerging digital market at the same time.

2. A digital catastrophe^[10]:

Many pharmaceutical companies have initiated digital platforms and promotions, but marketers cannot adopt an overall successful digital strategy in this area. Increased data has led to complicated research and the use of data in digital strategies has produced a digital disaster. Pharmaceutical vendors should unify data across channels; use data in real time, and digitally refine their thinking accordingly.

3. Strict Regulations:

The issue of the regulations in each jurisdiction needs careful consideration before digital campaigns are launched [11]. The marketing of life sciences faces more stringent regulations than other industries. The pharmaceutical industry must comply with the privacy standards of the FDA and the Federal Trade Commission (FTC) through the innovative copy. The Health Insurance Portability and Transparency Act (HIPAA) was established in 1996 to ensure the protection and privacy of health data. This act prohibited publicity providers from misusing health information online and protecting the privacy of healthcare records. In 2010, the FDA issued a warning letter to Novartis to pull the Facebook share as there was insufficient knowledge on risk of leukemia treatment Tassigna[12]. The drug companies have been more cautious in spending and implementing new digital marketing practices with their search restrictions [13].

Companies who are able to integrate digital and the approval process with built-in compliance workflows can make digital work in real-time^[10].

4. Poorly maintained websites:

Biopharmaceutical companies use social media slowly. Some of the pharmaceutical companies still follow the old "Web 1.0" world. The pharmaceutical industry has favored a one-way flow of information that has been closely monitored, legally accepted and shielded from external intervention. Such websites drive only details without direct patient interaction [14]. An outdated website with low maintenance is worse than no website. These interactions must be controlled with effective human resources [15].

Survey on Digital Marketing:

1. Survey conducted by COUCH^[8]:

COUCH, an integrated digital marketing and innovative medical communications firm, has carried out a survey of 119 pharmaceuticals companies to examine the threats the digital pharmaceutical industry will face in 2014.

1. 92 percent of respondents were not happy with the existing digital technology implementation of their businesses.
2. 83 percent of respondents face the difficulty of adopting emerging technology in their business
3. 75% of respondents described the budget as a major obstacle for integrating digitisation into their overall marketing strategy
4. 73% of respondents faced the lack of a digital workplace plan.

On a weekly basis, 14% of respondents assessed their behaviors. Respondents often referred to the big issues facing digital marketing. Know-how, ingenuity and imagination can be solved. Some include outsourcing to agencies, the use of contractors and part-time employees before sufficient funds are provided for full-time jobs or freelance workers.

The survey also centered on 2014's key priority to boost digital marketing in the pharmaceutical industry.

Nearly 95% of pharmaceutical companies recognize the value of websites, but some of them do not have one. The importance of marketing activities can be understood by calculating the return on investment that you get after this strategy has been adapted. Sales tools provide several options, such as customer relationship management (CRM), e-detailing programmes, and feed applications that enable the sales process to track prospects. Mobile is big in retail industries but not used in the pharmaceutical industry for marketing. 50% of respondents acknowledged the need for it as enormous but did not assess its suitability.

2. **Survey conducted by com SCORE** ^[9]: ComScore. NC, a pioneer in digital measurement, conducted an online marketing efficiency benchmark for pharmaceutical companies. Based on the survey data from comScore's 163 pharmaceutical reports, the findings indicate that online customer direct marketing (DTC) continues to improve patient conversion and prospects. It also indicates that the highest visibility rates of pharmaceutical online ads in any industry. According to a survey of millions of pharmaceutical publicity prints covering more than 15 brands, 51% of the advertisements were visible. Of the ten-industry benchmarked comScore, the highest visibility rates were pharmaceutical advertisement impressions.

3. Strategies that can be implemented

Pharmaceutical firms have a big chance to take advantage of their healthcare experience reforms by modifying their business model [16]. The pharmaceutical industry is a comprehensive information industry. The business model of healthcare has remained unchanged by the digital revolution until recently. Health has historically been distributed until now because the industry lacks digital technology [17]. Strict rules, lack of proper digital strategy, etc. have constituted major obstacles to digital marketing. The businesses need a clearly established digital

marketing plan, which most of them lack. Technology is not the only solution but can also be included in the daily workflow [18].

The following are the few strategies that pharmaceutical companies should take to maximize digital opportunities.

1. Collaborative business model^[19]:

Despite its conventional obstacles, the pharmaceutical industry is fast innovating through cooperation with investors, stakeholders and beyond. The availability of emerging technology offers enormous potential for almost infinite collaboration. The employees can study and create new treatments quickly and effectively. Pfizer, for example, has adopted an innovative cloud-based clinical database platform, which enables participants throughout studies and drug programs to compile, analyze and visualize clinical trial patient data supporting intelligent trial design, precision medicines, pharma co-vigilance and regulatory inquiries.

2. Business partners^[18]:

Digital solutions include partnerships with organizations that deal with complementary aspects of a particular illness. For example, companies selling auricular fibrillation anticoagulants should cooperate with medical device companies that recognise these cardiac remote control patients. It is not difficult to introduce a digital marketing method. Companies not only have to incorporate but also follow it.

3. Introduce mobile apps^[18]:

The pharmaceutical companies' long wait ended when the FDA issued guidelines on mobile medical applications. Apps provided by cell phones on a go will help patients better understand their diagnoses and medicines before they are discharged. Apps may provide complete details of any drug that enables better direct marketing for consumers. Pharmaceutical companies would be more profitable if they partners with enterprises that are able to offer apps in patient care, not specifically disease management, but symptoms and medicines.

Sharing data for population studies^[18]:

Big overtime data obtained appear to be worthless unless good analysis is conducted. The results of the data should be published. The integration of mobile and analytical treatment material would make a significant difference in healthcare.

4. Create a new organisational structure for digital marketing^[11]:

Appoint an electronic marketing campaign manager, an e-marketing product manager, a digital marketing committee, etc. to contribute to creative digital marketing of the business.

5. Ensure IT support^[11]:

Adequate IT support is needed in order to provide solution to any digital marketing issues.

6. Patient and Health Care Provider (HCP) services^[19]:

As patients and HCPs use more tools day after day, pharmaceutical companies often expect to offer technology-based services that can help patients monitor their health and control it. These programs will also contribute greatly to the research and creation of new therapies. It also ties stakeholders in the larger ecosystem of health

care to help and explain patient delivery. Patient services that are technologically accessible, like apps or online channels or educational tools that relate to a wider variety of services that assist patients and HCPs coping with health problems, should be exploited.

Future scopes:

In future, pharmaceutical companies will be highly digitalized and will establish extensive networking, data collection and collaboration. Soon, digital will become the cornerstone of the pharmaceutical industry as long as it establishes and implements proper marketing strategies. The engagement channel for brands will be provided by patients and healthcare teams. In our health system, the conventional one-way relationship will soon become a double-way relationship exclusively by means of digitalisation [20]. Mobile marketing, social media and other types of digital marketing can contribute to the development of useful platforms for the sharing of information by patients.

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ABOUT THE CONFERENCE

Creativity and innovations are indispensable for the growth of business and the success of the organization. It is an important factor which helps traditional companies and educational institutions in foreseeing the potential threats and rising competition. Needless to say, companies and organizations cannot thrive without matching the pace with the change and transformation which is taking place in the market. Digital transformation integrates digital technologies into all areas of a business. To meet with the ever changing demands of business processes and customer expectations and create a competitive advantage as well as positioning the organization for the future growth, the role of digital transformation and innovation cannot be ignored. IoT, Artificial Intelligence (AI), Automation, Machine Learning, Block Chain are some of the latest technologies which have brought about the sea of change by amalgamating demanding millennial generation into the high speed data lanes. In the past few months of Lockdown, digitalization has played a vital role in sustaining the global economic condition. Businesses are now looking for the new ways of dealings and cost minimization. Educational institutions also embraced digital mode of teaching and learning methodologies in order to minimize the impact of pandemic on the academics of students. This conference is intended to seek intellectual contribution of experts from industry, academia and research for embracing change & transformation through innovations and creativity.

ABOUT US

Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School runs AICTE approved PGDM program. It has been ranked 1st Emerging B-School among top institutes of west India by Time of India. It has also been conferred the ET Now Business School of the year award. The two-year full-time PGDM program offered by Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School is designed to empower students to become successful business professionals in the challenging global scenario. The Institute is continually evolving to meet its goals in an ever-changing business environment. It has been playing an important role in professionalizing Indian Management through its programs. Dr. D. Y. Patil B-School aims to create value-driven leaders, global managers and entrepreneurs with strong conceptual foundations and analytical approach to help them be the best in whichever field they choose. The aim is to innovatively address the needs of a modern India and connecting aspirations and realities to attain benchmarks that are respected internationally.

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